

STUDIES IN INDIGOID DYES. PART IV

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The 7-methyl derivatives of *bis*-2-thionaphthene-ethylene-indigo and of 2-thionaphthene-1'-aceanthrylene-indigo have been prepared. Their dyeing shades on wool and on cotton have been found lighter than those obtained from the corresponding 4-, 5- and 6-methyl compounds.

7-Methyl derivative of benzylidene-2-thianaphthene and some of its substituted products have been prepared. Their dyeing shades have been found lighter than those obtained from the corresponding substances of the 4-, and 5-methyl series but deeper than those obtained from the corresponding 6-methyl compounds.

From the examination of colour and dyeing properties of a large number of isomeric indole-(methyl)-thionaphthene-indigos and all the isomeric dimethyl-thioindigos, it was deduced that their depth of colour decreases as the methyl group is shifted from 5 to 4 to 6 to 7-position of the thionaphthene nucleus of the molecule of the dye and also observed that the depth of colour of the parent compound of each series is next to that of its 5-methyl derivative (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **21**, 87).

With a view to testing further how far this observation is applicable to other thioindigoid dyes of asymmetrical as well as symmetrical structure, 2-thionaphthene-1'-aceanthrylene-indigo and *bis*-2-thionaphthene-ethylene-indigo (D.P. 250157, 253762; Friedlander and Risse, *Ber.*, 1914, **47**, 1919) were selected as respective examples.

The influence of a methyl group in 4-, 5-, and 6-position of the thionaphthene nucleus of the parent dye in each of the two above mentioned series was already studied in previous parts of this series (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 658; 1937, **14**, 709; 1938, **15**, 359). In the present communication the effect of a methyl group in the 7-position of the thionaphthene ring of *bis*-2-thionaphthene-ethylene-indigo and 2-thionaphthene-1'-aceanthrylene-indigo has been studied.

7-Methyl-3-hydroxy-thionaphthene (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 37) has been condensed with glyoxal and aceanthrenequinone respectively. The two new vat dyes are crystalline deep red and dark red substances. Their dyeing shades on wool and on cotton have been found lighter than those obtained from the isomeric 4-, 5- and 6-methyl derivatives. In both the series this qualitative inference has been verified by measuring the absorption spectra of the dyes in xylene solution and calculating the absorption maxima (Table I) from their absorption curves (Figs. 1, 2 and 3).

It is, therefore, summarised from the detailed study of all the theoretically possible isomeric *bis*-(methyl)-thionaphthene-ethylene-indigos and (methyl)-thionaphthene-aceanthrylene-indigos (Table I) that the 5-methyl products are the deepest of all, second is the position of the 4-methyl compounds, the 6-methyl products occupy the third position and the lightest are the 7-methyl-indigos. The parent dye *bis*-2-thionaphthene-ethylene-indigo is lighter only than its 5-methyl derivative.

It is thus found that the relation between colour and chemical constitution of all the isomeric *bis*-(methyl)-thionaphthene-ethylene-indigos and (methyl) thionaphthene-aceanthrylene-indigos deduced now is in good agreement with what was already found by the author in case of quite a number of isomeric indole-(methyl)-thionaphthene-indigos and all the isomeric dimethyl-thioindigos (Guha, *loc. cit.*).

The different shades of the isomeric *bis*-(methyl) thionaphthene-ethylene-indigos on wool and on cotton are beautiful but that of the 6-methyl compound is particularly pleasing and attracting.

In Tables I, II and III, M = Methyl, T = Thionaphthene, B = Benzylidene.

TABLE I

Compounds.	Absorption maxima.	Compounds.	Absorption maxima.
<i>bis</i> -2-T-ethylene-indigo	4835Å	2 (4-M)-T-acceanthrylene-indigo	4455Å
<i>bis</i> -2-(4-M)-T-ethylene-indigo	4810	2-(5-M)-T-acceanthrylene-indigo	4400
<i>bis</i> -2-(5-M)-T-ethylene-indigo	4920	2-(6-M)-T-acceanthrylene-indigo	445Q
<i>bis</i> -2-(6-M)-T-ethylene-indigo	4765	2-(7-M)-T-acceanthrylene-indigo	4410
<i>bis</i> -2-(7-M)-T-ethylene-indigo	4750		

When the studies in the isomeric (methyl)-thionaphthene-acceanthrylene-indigos were made complete, it struck that the corresponding compounds belonging to acenaphthenequinone series, the (methyl)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos are much deeper in colour (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 91). This led the author to conclude that as the complexity of the right half of the molecule of 2-thionaphthene-8'-acenaphthyleneindigo (I) is increased by fusing another six-membered ring into it, when for example 2-thionaphthene-1'-acceanthrylene indigo (II) is produced, the depth of colour of the new product is lightened which will be understood clearly from the instances cited under Table II.

TABLE II

Compounds.	Dyeing shade on wool.	Compounds.	Dyeing shade on wool.
2-T-8'-acenaphthylene-indigo	Scarlet	2-(6-M)-T-8'-acenaphthylene-indigo	Vermillion
2-T-1'-acceanthrylene-indigo	Orange brown	2-(6-M)-T-1'-acceanthrylene-indigo	Red brown
2-(4-M)-T-8'-acenaphthylene-indigo	Vermillion	2-(7-M)-T-8'-acenaphthylene-indigo	Dark red
2-(4-M)-T-1'-acceanthrylene-indigo	Dark-brown	2-(7-M)-T-8'-acceanthrylene-indigo	Red brown
2-(5-M)-T-8'-acenaphthylene-indigo	Scarlet red		
2-(5-M)-T-8'-acceanthrylene-indigo	Orange-brown		

A few thioindogenides have been prepared by condensing 7-methyl-3-hydroxy-thionaphthene with benzaldehyde, *p*-nitro-, and its *p*-dimethylamino derivative respectively. The aldehydes used in this 7-methyl series are the same as those used in the case of the corresponding 4-, 5-, and 6-methyl series described in parts I, II and III, for the convenience of a comparative study. The thioindogenides of the 7-methyl series are also coloured products which were obtained easily in crystalline form. They resemble the other isomeric methyl compounds in giving rise to characteristic colour by the action of concentrated sulphuric acid. The dyeing shades of all these substances on wool from an acid bath are fully and uniformly developed. But their shades do not appear fully on cotton from the alkaline hydrosulphite vat although they are uniform [*cf.* the isomeric benzylidene-(methyl) thionaphthenes. Guha, *loc. cit.*]

These shades are found lighter than those obtained from the corresponding 4- and 5-methyl compounds but deeper than those obtained from the corresponding 6-methyl products. The absorption curves (Fig. 4) and the absorption maxima (Table III) confirm the qualitative

FIG. 1

Fig. 1. Bis-2-(7-methyl)-thionaphthene-ethylene indigo.

- 2. x and y refer respectively to 2-(5-methyl)-, and 2-(4-methyl)-thionaphthene-1'-acanthrylene indigo.
- 3. v and w refer respectively to 2-(7-methyl) and 2-(6-methyl)-thionaphthene-1'-anathrylene indigo.
- 4. Benzylidene-2(7-methyl)-thionaphthene.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

observation. Hence the relation between colour and chemical constitution of the isomeric benzylidene-(methyl) thionaphthenes is found similar to that of the isomeric methyl thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos (Guha, *loc. cit.*)

Of the various isomeric benzylidene-(methyl) thionaphthenes prepared, 4'-nitro-benzylidene-2-(5-methyl)-thionaphthene and all the isomeric 4'-dimethylamino-benzylidene-(methyl) thionaphthenes exhibit pleasant shade. It is found that none of the coloured products of the thioindogenide series, studied by the author, possess any value as vat dyes but all of them develop well on wool from an acid bath.

TABLE III

Compounds.	Absorption maxima.
B-2(4-M)-T	4400 Å
B-2(5-M)-T	4445
B-2(6-M)-T	4320
B-2(7-M)-T	4370

EXPERIMENTAL

bis-2-(7-Methyl) thionaphthene-ethylene-indigo.

A solution of glyoxal sodium bisulphite (1'136 g.) in distilled water (30 c.c.) was mixed with 7-methyl-3-hydroxy-thionaphthene (1'312 g.) dissolved in hot absolute alcohol (40 c.c.). The mixture on treatment with concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) and heating on the water-bath for 1½ hours, gave a violet-red crystalline precipitate, which was filtered, washed with alcohol and hot water, yield 0'737 g. The dye was crystallised from xyliene in deep red microscopic needles and also from pyridine in stout thin rectangles, not melting below 312°. It is difficultly soluble in toluene and chloroform; sparingly soluble in acetone, carbon tetrachloride, alcohol; moderately soluble in acetic acid. The solution of this dye in concentrated sulphuric acid is yellowish-green. It dyes cloth in violet-red shade from a deep yellow alkaline hydrosulphite vat and wool in dark-red shade from an acid bath. (Found: S, 18'27. C₂₀H₁₄O₂S₂ requires S, 18'28 per cent).

2-(7-Methyl)-thionaphthene-1'-aceanthrylene-indigo.

The hot solution of aceanthrenequinone (0.696 g.) and 7-methyl-3-hydroxy-thionaphthene (0.492 g.) in 80 c.c. of glacial acetic acid was treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (sp. gr. 1.12, 5 c.c.). The mixture was boiled for 15 to 20 minutes in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide. The separated red product (0.75 g.) was collected while the solution was still hot. It is soluble in aniline and chloroform; difficultly soluble in pyridine, xylene and acetic acid; insoluble in alcohol. It was crystallised from a large volume of xylene in foliated shining dark red needles not melting below 304°. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it with yellowish-green solution from which the original red substance is precipitated on the addition of water. It dyes wool in light red-brown shade from an acid bath and cotton in light red-ochre from a yellowish-green hydrosulphite vat. (Found: S, 8.11. $C_{25}H_{14}O_2S$ requires S, 8.46 per cent).

Benzylidene-2-(7-methyl)-thionaphthene.—It separated on boiling for 15 minutes benzaldehyde (0.424 g.) 7-methyl-3-hydroxy-thionaphthene (0.656 g.) in 13 c. c. of hot absolute alcohol, with concentrated hydrochloric acid (2 c.c.) The brownish-yellow product (0.741 g.) was crystallised from dilute alcohol in long rectangles, m.p. 130°. It is soluble in benzene, acetone and alcohol. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it producing a deep brownish red solution. It dyes wool in yellow shade from an acid bath. (Found: S, 12.89. $C_{16}H_{12}OS$ requires S, 12.69 per cent).

4'-Nitro-benzylidene-2-(7-methyl)-thionaphthene was obtained as yellow-orange small rectangular precipitate by boiling for 15 minutes a solution of *p*-nitro-benzaldehyde (0.453 g.) and 7-methyl-3-hydroxy-thionaphthene (0.492 g.) dissolved in 26 c.c. of absolute alcohol and concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 c.c.) The coloured substance (0.7345 g.) was crystallised from acetic acid in rectangles, m.p. 247°. It is moderately soluble in alcohol, difficultly soluble in acetone. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid producing a blue solution. It dyes cotton in light orange shade from a light brown alkaline hydrosulphite vat and wool in deep yellow shade from an acid bath. (Found: S, 11.0. $C_{18}H_{11}O_3NS$ requires S, 10.77 per cent).

4'-Dimethylamino-benzylidene-2-(7-methyl)-thionaphthene was obtained as its hydrochloride as a greenish-yellow crystalline precipitate by similarly boiling a red-brown solution of *p*-dimethylamino-benzaldehyde (0.596 g.) and 7-methyl-3-hydroxy-thionaphthene (0.656 g.) in 17 c.c. of absolute alcohol and 2 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. It gave on washing with dilute alcohol the vermilion product (0.727 g.). It was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in wooly needles, m.p. 150°. It is soluble in alcohol and acetone. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it with a blue-violet solution which on dilution with a little water turns yellow and when largely diluted gives the red precipitate of the original substance. It dyes cloth in pink colour from a faintly red alkaline hydrosulphite vat and wool in bright orange-red shade from an acid bath. (Found: S, 11.21. $C_{18}H_{17}ONS$ requires S, 10.84 per cent).

The author's thanks are due to Mr. K. Prasad I.E.S. and Dr. R. C. Ray D.Sc. for their interest in this work and to Messrs. D. K. Bhattacharya M.Sc. and K. S. Manian (Calcutta) for helping with spectrograph and microphotometer.